

Indigenization, decolonization, and reconciliation in mathematics education

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The aim of the study was to explore mathematics teacher educators' views on indigenization, decolonization and reconciliation in Nepalese classroom context. Three universities teachers' educators were selected purposively. A qualitative-interpretive inquiry was used as a research method to conduct in-depth semi-structured interviews with three teacher educators. The interview data was transcribed and read several times, for constructing themes and subthemes. The major themes of the study were: local mathematics in indigenous knowledge, indigenous for meaningful mathematical concept, indigenization for ownership of learning, decolonization as an empowerment, and reconciliation in the emerging context.

Introduction

The term indigenous knowledge (IK) describes local, culturally specific knowledge unique to a certain population at a place. IK is often depicted as being alive, in current use, and transmitted orally (Simonds & Christopher, 2013). IK may come from the development field to describe, for example, agricultural methods or uses for botanicals that come from local knowledge (Simonds & Christopher, 2013).

Decolonization requires teachers to know Indigenous worldview to illustrate the connections among reconciliation efforts, decolonization, education, and the science of story work (Macmath & Hall, 2018). Similarly, an approach might be employed not only in social studies contexts, but also in the sciences and mathematics in the provision of notions such as re-inhabiting, decolonizing, Indigenizing, and reconciling to work with marginalized rural students (Lowan-Trudeau, 2017). Decolonization, however, is a broader concept that encompasses actions and processes that counteract, reverse, or terminate all of these phenomena. Claiming that decolonization was a partial and multi-layered process, comprising different elements, causes and consequences, still requires us to situate the phenomenon in time and space (Collins, 2016).

IK involves all students, teachers and community members. Indigenization as a discourse through academic writing and research emerged the early 2000s (Mihesuah & Wilson, 2004) and has increased in scope and depth to become a globally transformative movement.

Reconciliation is improving the relationship between indigenous students and non-indigenous students in the classroom. It helps to rebuild trust, avoid blame each other.

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Similarly, Willie Ermine (2007) argues about the ways in which these processes are related, explaining that reconciling Indigenous and Western worldviews. Reconciliation is complex; it means different things to different people. Canada's Royal Commission on Aboriginal Peoples (1996) outlined a straightforward definition more than twenty years ago: "Canada must dispense with all notions of superiority, assimilation, and subordination and develop a new relationship with Aboriginal peoples based on sharing, mutual recognition, respect, and responsibility" (Battiste, 2013, p. 26).

Decolonization in mathematics education

Indigenous education has to be linked to "antiracism and social justice" (Government of British Columbia, 2015a, p. 13). Reconciliation requires coming to terms with schooling as a tool of colonialism that has harmed indigenous people. The school system was designed to maintain and impose colonial language, culture, and identity (Battiste, 2013, p. 30). Bringing indigenous culture into the school systems without first decolonizing relationships can be used to mask racial logic as the bringing in of indigenous culture does not acknowledge white settler privilege, colonial injustices, and practices of erasure (Battiste, 2013). Decolonization requires a "deconstruction and a reconstruction" (Battiste, 2013, p. 10). The indigenous renaissance has deconstructed and discredited the traditional Eurocentric views of indigenous peoples and their heritage as exotic objects that have nothing to do with knowledge, science, or progress. However, it has not displaced the educational empire of European knowledge (Battiste & Henderson, 2009).

Indigenous pedagogy

Indigenous pedagogy seems essential to teaching mathematics for meaningful understanding. It may support students in valuing their mathematics learning experiences. Similarly, the British Columbia Ministry of Education identified seven principles necessary to "integrate Aboriginal world views and knowledges" and their rationale (BC Ministry of Education, 2013, p. 3). A teacher should integrate IK in mathematics curriculum with teaching activities. He or she can relate the mathematical concepts to local materials and cultural artefacts. Teachers should foster positive relationships with diverse students, between students, and individual to individual.

Integrating indigenous knowledge

The framework of learning for integrating IK supports integration of IK with mathematics. It guides teaching and learning to enhance students' learning in mathematics. One of such frameworks is The First Peoples Principles of Learning (FPPL) implemented in BC curriculum (FNESC, 2011). This focuses on action, reflection, integration and connection of mathematics contents to local knowledge. So, it is useful in our diverse cultural context.

Mathematics teachers can use local learning materials for giving meaningful mathematical concepts. For instance, teachers can follow the FPPL while integrating IK in

mathematics depending on local social and cultural context. However, there is less practice of integrating IK and pedagogy in mathematics classroom in Nepal and many other places.

The purpose of this study was to explore the mathematics educators' perception and practice of indigenization, decolonization and reconciliation in Nepalese classroom context. The research question was: How do teachers perceive and practice of indigenization, decolonization and Reconciliation in mathematics class room?

Review of literature

From Indigenous perspectives, indigenization of the academy refers to the meaningful inclusion of Indigenous knowledge(s), in the everyday fabric of the institution from policies to practices across all levels, not just in curriculum. Marlene Brant Castellano (2014) envisions Indigenized education to mean that every subject at every level is examined to consider how and to what extent current content and pedagogy reflect the presence of Indigenous/Aboriginal peoples and the valid contribution of Indigenous knowledge. Mihesuah and Wilson's (2004) *Indigenizing the Academy: Transforming scholarship and empowering communities* is one of the first texts put forward by Indigenous scholars who reflect on what it meant to indigenize the academy. Those students and scholars re-claiming their Aboriginal identity as a decolonization process (Pidgeon, 2016).

Teachers can practice mathematics teaching and learning through integrating IK and pedagogy in the classroom. In doing this, students can more easily perceive the mathematical concepts and ideas. These practices can help to evolve ownership of the subject. We can deconstruct mathematics pedagogy and knowledge and integrate the indigenous knowledge. Similarly, Pidgeon (2016) concluded that non-Aboriginal peoples must take responsibility and be part of their own decolonizing process and move towards reconciliation. In an Indigenized institution, Indigenous peoples remain empowered in their self-determination and cultural integrity. I want to know how best the teachers helps to indigenize the classrooms. Teaching may be effective and meaningful if teachers connect mathematical concepts with local knowledge and cultures. In our context, every mathematics students and teacher might evolve their own identity through decolonization process. However, it is challenging due to the dominance of western colonization. I think indigenization focuses on study of aboriginal students. Indeed, reconciliation will require mutual learning from, between, and across Indigenous and Western knowledge systems, without privileging Western knowledge, or appropriating IK through training and education. It must respect and recognize the diversity of Indigenous approaches (Levac et al., 2018).

It is important to acknowledge indigenous students through reconciliation with Greenwood's pillars of decolonization and reinhabitation (Lowan-Trudeau, 2017). There are two underlying assumptions of the policies on cultural diversity and culturally inclusive learning: (a) individual differences caused by various socio-cultural factors have to be managed in terms of individual equity and (b) individual stakeholders are required to have the self-awareness ability to participate in cultural diversity. These assumptions are completely opposite to Indigenous collectively homogeneous approaches to learning. In IK

contexts, individual needs are aligned with community as collective consciousness through interrelatedness and interconnectedness (Dreamson, Thomas, Hong, & Kim, 2017). In my opinion, we can evolve mathematics according to the needs of our society.

It is believed that indigenous knowledge, in general, can be used to promote the teaching of mathematics in multicultural classes. We can use game for the identification of mathematics concepts on enjoyable way and it develops Spontaneous interaction, association of competition, enjoyment and recreation amongst students as they communicate their activities to fellow participants (Nkopodi & Mosimege, 2009).

A dialogic process develops strong community partnerships, creates opportunities for cultural exchange between stakeholders, and supports their equal involvement in planning, delivering and evaluating learning and teaching (Dreamson, Thomas, Hong, & Kim, 2017). The concepts of interrelatedness and interconnectedness determine Indigenous holistic pedagogies and form the metaphysical foundations for understanding interculturality, culturally inclusive learning is more than ensuring equal participation of students from culturally diverse backgrounds because equity is culturally bound.

Some Balinese cultural elements: ceniga, the yard size based on asta kosala-kosali, and also the pattern of Legong dancer position were used in teaching suitable plane figure geometry and practical formulas are taught to the students (Wijayanti, Sunardi, Tirta, Margaretha & Wijaya, 2019).

Mediation plays a significant role in learning mathematics. It suggests that children learn from others and society through active interactions and participation in activities in groups. Scaffolding and guidance are necessary for learners. "Vygotsky described the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) as a distance between child's ability in independent problem solving and potential ability of problem-solving with guidance" (Panthi & Belbase, 2017, p. 4). Habermasian technical, practical and emancipatory interest emphasized three ways of knowing are empirical-analytic, historical hermeneutic and emancipatory. This theory focuses on contents, meaning making and critical thinking. I employed this theory in my study. The task of empirical analytic science incorporates technical cognitive interest; historical-hermeneutic science incorporates practical interest, and the approach of critically oriented science incorporates the emancipatory cognitive interest (Habermas, 1972, as cited in Grundy, 1987, p. 10). The practical interest is defined as a fundamental interest in understanding environments through interaction based upon a consensual interpretation of meaning (Grundy, 1987). Historical-hermeneutic knowing is meaning making from historical records or literary.

Research method

I employed a qualitative-interpretive inquiry as research method. 'Interpretation' within a hermeneutic study is not an easily described data analysis method. Van Manen (1990) explicate interpretation as a "free act of seeing meaning" (p. 79) within the data. I chose three teacher educators from three universities was purposefully selected for each university in the Kathmandu district. I employed open ended interview questions; each interview lasted

about 35 minutes. I transcribed the recorded text data into Nepali and then into English. I read transcription in several times and applied thematic analysis to constructs themes and subthemes. A hermeneutic process of interpretation required reflexivity with questions on, data collected and its interpretation (Berger, 2015). I used pseudonyms of my participants as Chintan, Manan and Utkhanan for anonymity.

Results and discussion

Five themes emerged from text data – local mathematics in indigenous knowledge, indigenous for meaningful mathematical concept, indigenization for ownership of learning, decolonization as an empowerment, and reconciliation in the emerging context. I discussed each theme by connecting to praxis, as the interplay between theory and practice (Panthi, Luitel & Belbase, 2018) as follows:

Local mathematics in indigenous knowledge

I asked first question to my participants, what is your views about indigenous knowledge of mathematics? The following excerpts are samples of participants' views on this question:

Chintan: IK is a vague term. It includes students' prior knowledge, we integrate IK on western mathematics for knowing the concepts clearly and it is necessary for learning mathematics. We can use the indigenous mathematics representation as a basis for learning western mathematics. If we develop the base of IK of current mathematics, it helps to develop the concepts and meaning understanding of the subjects. Moreover, it supports a new form of learning concepts and coherence of learning mathematics. It is an essential for us. It comes more or less in our classroom practice (Interview, 13th May, 2020). He emphasizes that IK is a basis for meaningful understanding of modern mathematics.

Manan: IK is that which includes matters of agricultural, Industries, poultry, metal works, jewellery, transaction which includes exchange system gives the concepts profit and loss, counting system which includes measurement. He focuses on creating meaningful environment and teachers' gives task according to students' interest. We think whether it is creating mathematical reasoning or not, it is the intentionally creating but not naturally evolved (Interview, 14th May, 2020). The very existence of all things – mountains and waterholes, plants and animals, ourselves and our languages, the way we live – is evidence of the actions of the creator ancestors (Love, Moore, & Warburton, 2017).

Chintan: The dominance of western knowledge exists in our mathematics. If you ask question to the students, they can share their experiences. Teacher: What is a circle and circular shape? Student: circle is a two dimensional figure with fixed point and fixed distance from that point, such as bottom of Theki, Sikka, Nanglo (Nepalese Local name of indigenous objects). It is easy to learn mathematics integrating indigenous knowledge. We emphasis to develop thinking knowledge of our students. We can ask questions about cylinder, cylindrical shape such Theki, Dhungro, Madal (Nepalese Local name of indigenous objects) etc. teacher can create an environment to discuss about things which the students have already knowing

objects in the classroom and link with mathematical concepts. (Interview, 13th May, 2020). He argues that students give reasoning mathematical concepts to the local objects.

Using indigenous ways of knowing in research methods is different from using or benefiting from indigenous or cultural knowledge per se. Nonetheless, the use of Indigenous ways of knowing to better understand a topic—to make an impact on eliminating health disparities, for instance—may lead to the exposure of IK and the challenges we have raised in this essay (Cochran et al., 2008).

Indigenous knowledge for meaningful mathematical concept

I asked second question to my participants, how do you use indigenous knowledge for meaningful mathematical concept? The participants' views on this question have been presented in the following excerpts:

Chintan: IK is necessary for early knowledge, easy to form concepts, coherent learning, develop ownership learning, students friendly learning, respectful learning, cultural respect learning, shared learning, discussing learning, western approaches such as inquiry based approached, constructivist approach, project based approached support to investigate Indigenous knowledge. It is easy to integrate IK through progressive approach in the classroom and vice-versa indigenous approaches (Interview, 13th May, 2020). He viewed that IK is valuable for meaningful and effective learning.

Manan: We should promote IK which can use for understanding the power, nature and application in mathematics. We can apply it if it supports to understand abstractness of mathematics. We should provide knowledge of mathematics to the students for making competent and skilful in the world. We should preserve indigenous ways of knowing (Interview, 13th May, 2020). It is used in modern mathematics for enjoyment on meaningful learning. The most significant aspect of decolonization is a process of historical and ideological change (Collins, 2016) in mathematics teaching and learning.

Reconciliation in the emerging context

I asked third question to my participants, what is your views about reconciliation in the emerging context of mathematics education in practice? The participants' views have been presented as:

Chintan: Reconciliation is process of building relationships, making different mathematical concepts as whole content and making compatible. It is the relationship between knowledge level and pedagogical level, it is also a two-way relation between progressive approaches and indigenous approaches. There is a relationship between IK and western knowledge. There is a friendly relationship between students and teacher. It is easy to transform learning. It emphasizes the relationship from individual to individual, teacher to students, knowledge to practice (Interview, 13th May, 2020). It focuses on building a relationship between teachers to students, students to students, students to society, teacher to society, individual to individual. The reconciliation is changes outside remedial relations

between Indigenous and non-Indigenous peoples in terms of past destruction (Lowan-Trudeau, 2017) of cultures and land. Manan and Utkhanan supports this view.

Decolonization as an empowerment

I asked fourth question to my participants, what is your views about decolonization as empowerment in mathematics from local practice? A sample of participants' views have been presented in the following excerpt:

Chintan: The concepts of decolonization come from Latin America. It is the reclaiming, reviving, challenging, making on practice of native languages as a medium of instruction, cultures, approaches, knowledge of the mathematical concepts. It is a response, reject of colonial ideas. It is similar with anti-colonial thoughts. However, there are two type of colonization such as physical and ideological. We discuss here with ideological colonization or mind colonization. We are guided by others, we have no new thoughts of our own. We have colonized thoughts. If we develop own ideas in mathematics knowledge, that can be a decolonizing practice. We can practice own practice such as Gurukul (traditional teaching) practice. It is challenging on our structure (Interview, 13th May, 2020). He focuses on deconstruct mathematics knowledge and pedagogy. Decolonization focuses on a practical (local context) or intellectual problems (Collins, 2016) in mathematics teaching and learning. Chinn (2007) found that critical professional development employing decolonizing methodologies articulated by indigenous researchers Abbott and Smith has the potential to raise teachers' awareness of the connections among personal and place-based experiences, cultural practices and values, and teaching and learning.

Indigenization for Ownership of Learning

I asked fifth question to my participants, what is your views about indigenization for ownership of learning mathematics in local practice? The following excerpts show the participants' views:

Manan: We cannot say that our mathematics is western mathematics because anyone can add new knowledge. For instance, base 10 system is Hindu mathematics. So, mathematics is common domain where it includes mathematics of every cultures. For instance, Euclid can collect mathematics in thirteen elements where it contains mathematics of various cultures such as Eastern and Western. Mathematics is a large bag. It is expanding different time periods in different places. Parallel lines, perpendicular lines, straight lines are included in eastern mathematics and even in western mathematics knowledge. (Interview, 14th May, 2020). He highlighted on our gurukul system which focuses on rote memorization and different mathematical concepts, He believes that modern mathematics includes IK and it is a large bag. We can also connect indigenous mathematics and pedagogy on modern mathematics for making practical in our cultural context.

Furthermore, Mana said: Indigenous Knowledge depends on for what, for why. Do we practice IK our children? We focus on value of mathematics. It is better to use to connect our mathematics for learning easily, procedural understanding, increasing motivation level and

raising questioning. Other beauties of mathematics is abstract reasoning. There are some challenges for teaching logarithmic functions, exponential functions using IK (Interview, 14th May, 2020).

Utkhanan: We synchronize IK into modern mathematics. We should not detach IK from modern mathematics. We learn mathematics from our own ways. We adapt with new knowledge relate to our indigenous knowledge. We can use story telling method, telling poem, telling song, wring genre etc to develop the concepts of mathematics. However, Chandrakala Devi Dhananjaya, who is the first mathematician, she wrote poem related about mathematics. She did not generate meaning. She believes in gaining knowledge by rote memorization. We can use indigenous pedagogy in mathematics classroom (Interview, 14th May, 2020). He views that we can use various strategies to construct generate mathematics knowledge meaningfully associated with local knowledge such as mathematics on temple, artefacts, Doko, Ring, Tauwa, Ping, Nepali musical instruments.

Insightful thoughts

IK is a bases for western mathematics learning meaningfully. It is an essential for developing new knowledge and pedagogies. It evolves ownership of teaching and learning mathematics. Teachers synchronize IK of knowing into modern mathematics. For instance, they can show Nanglo, Sikka for the concepts of circle and they can also demonstrate dhungro, Theki for the concepts of cylinder. Use of IK makes mathematics meaningful and developing ownerships. Indigenization is the process of reflection of current content and pedagogy in terms of indigenous knowledge. It is also a reflection practice between teachers to students, between students, individual to individual in the classroom. Furthermore, decolonization is the reclaiming, revive, challenging, making on practice on own languages, cultures, approaches, knowledge of the mathematical concepts. Similarly, reconciliation is process of building relationship, making different mathematical concepts to whole, making compatible.

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